

**MURZINIA KARATAUENSIS, N. GEN., N. SP. (COLEOPTERA:
CERAMBYCIDAE: LAMIINAE: MONOCHAMINI)
FROM KAZAKHSTAN**

Maxim A. Lazarev*

* Bolshaia Serpuhovskaia str. 34, building 4, apartment 79, Moscow 115093 RUSSIA. E-mail: cerambycidae@fromru.com

[Lazarev, M. A. 2011. *Murzinia karatauensis*, n. gen., n. sp. (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Lamiini: Monochamini) from Kazakhstan. *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 6 (2): 639-641]

ABSTRACT: *Murzinia*, gen. nov. is similar to *Monochamus* Dejean, 1821, but strongly differs by the presence of a row of semierect strong setae along ventral side of 3rd-4th antennal joints. *M. karatauensis*, sp. n. from north Karatau Ridge (South Kazakhstan) is totally brown with irregular white spots.

KEY WORDS: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, *Murzinia*, new genus, new species, Kazakhstan.

The discovery of a new big Cerambycidae in Kazakhstan is quite unexpected and very interesting. *Murzinia karatauensis*, gen. nov., sp. nov. from North Karatau Ridge (South Kazakhstan) is not similar to any other taxon. The unique animal was preserved for many years in the collection of S. Murzin (Moscow) and now generously presented to the Zoological Museum of Moscow University.

DESCRIPTION

***MURZINIA*, gen. nov.**

Type species: ***Murzinia karatauensis*, sp. n.**

Eyes deeply emarginated, finally faceted (similar to *Monochamus*); apical palpi joints strongly elongated; female antennae longer than body; cicatrix strongly developed, totally closed; 3rd antennal joint is longer than 4th and much longer than 1st; 3rd-4th joints with a row of semierect strong short setae along ventral side (Fig. 2); a group of similar setae is situated near the apex of 1st joint; several scattered semierect setae present along ventral side of 5th-7th joints; apical 11th joint with a distinct distal contraction; prothorax transverse with very long and stout lateral spines not curved backwards; pronotum with well developed post-medial tubercle and two anterior convexities; prothoracic intercoxal process regularly convex; anterior coxal cavities closed; mesothoracic intercoxal process rounded apically, parallelsided; each elytron independently rounded apically; metathoracic episternae elongated, strongly narrowed; middle and hind tibiae with distinct lateral grooves; tarsal claws simple, without teeth, not divaricate.

One species known.

***Murzinia karatauensis*, sp. n.**

(Figs. 1-2)

Type locality. Kzyl-Orda Region, Chilli District, North Karatau Ridge, Daut Mountain.

Diagnosis. A single female known (Fig. 1); body totally red-brown including antennae and legs; head and thorax a little darker; head, thorax, abdomen and legs with fine white pubescence and scattered big dots surrounded by glabrous rings; frons subquadrate; genae about two times shorter than ventral eye lobe; the distance between dorsal eye lobes about equal to the width of the base of 1st antennal joint; antennae surpassing body by 4 apical joints; 1st joint strongly dilated apically, covered with fine white pubescence, with several big dots surrounded by glabrous rings; other joints without big dots and glabrous circles; prothorax about 1.3 times wider at base than long; pronotum with two big anterior spots of dense yellow setae, two small posterior spot and irregular lateral yellow areas; post-medial pronotal tubercle glabrous; scutellum triangular with very dense yellow pubescens; elytra about 2.1 times longer than wide; shining; with scattered regular punctation; dots are partly longitudinally arranged, without glabrous circles; fine pubescence partly condensed forming irregular white areas; two oblique diffused yellow stripes present near humery; 1st joint of hind tarsi about as long as 2nd and 3rd together and about equal to the last joint; 3rd joint about as long as wide, emarginated to about base, with elongated lobes; abdominal tergite slightly emarginated; last abdominal sternite truncated; body length: 28.3 mm; body width: 6.1 mm.

Distribution. Only one locality known in South Kazakhstan: Kzyl-Orda Region, Chiili District, North Karatau Ridge, Daut Mountain.

Material. Holotype, female with 2 labels: 1) [Kzyl-Orda Reg., Chiili Distr., North Karatau Ridge, near Daut Mt., 19.09.1964, I. Sukacheva] [in Russian]; 2) *Monochamus* sp. det. S. Murzin. The holotype is preserved in Zoological Museum of Moscow State University.

Etymology. The name of the new genus is dedicated to a well known Russian entomologist Sergey Murzin, who supplied me with the specimen for description. The species name formed on the base of the name of the native mountain system - Karatau.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I am very grateful to Sergey Murzin for providing me with the specimen for study.

Figures 1-2. *Murzinia karatauensis*, **sp. n.** 1 - female, holotype; 2 - basal antennal joints.